

Questionnaire ‘Study of the Impact of Perceptions of Human Mortality on the Motivation of Employees in Organizations Dealing with Memorialization and Collective Memory in Ukraine’

The purpose of the study is to understand why workers in high psychological pressure areas do their jobs. The following questionnaire is based on developments in the *terror management theory* and social psychology, and M. Heidegger’s phenomenology. The findings aim to improve understanding of employee motivation and resilience in contexts marked by human suffering.

This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the University of Tsukuba (Japan) on December 15th, 2023. It is **completely anonymous**, and its results will not be used for commercial purposes, but **only for general analytical scientific purposes**. Once the survey results are included in the final analysis, the resulting data will be permanently deleted from our records. Participants’ individual **responses will not be disclosed to any third party**.

Participation in the study is completely voluntary and you can withdraw at any time.

If you have any questions or comments about the content of this study, please contact the authors.

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I. Background Information

1. Please specify your age.

- under 20
- 20-25
- 26-35
- 36-45
- 46-55
- over 55

2. Please specify your gender.

- Female.
- Male.
- Other (please specify_____)

3. In which organization do you work?

- Babyn Yar Holocaust Memorial Center
- Past / Future / Art
- "The Territory of Terror" Memorial Museum
- Museum "Remembrance of the Jewish People to the Holocaust in Ukraine"
- Ukrainian Center for the Holocaust Studies (UCHS)
- National Museum of the History of Ukraine in the Second World War
- National Holodomor Genocide Museum
- Holocaust Museum (Kremenchuk)
- National Historical and Memorial Reserve "Babyn Yar"
- National Museum-Memorial of Victims of the Occupation Regimes "Loncky Street Prison"
- Mnemonics
- Ukrainian National Chernobyl Museum
- "Memorial" Memory Platform
- Other (please specify_____)

4. What is your field of activity within the organization?

- Research work (scientific work, work with archives, etc.)
- Administrative work (finance, HR, jurisprudence, IT, public relations, etc.)
- Museum work (conducting tours, working with exhibitions, etc.)
- Publishing house (proofreading or editorial work, etc.)
- Communicating with people (psychologist, making a list of needs, communicating with people who need it, etc.)

Other (please specify _____)

5. How long have you been working with it?

Under 1 year

1 to 3 years

4 to 5 years

Over 5 years

6. Rate your self-esteem.

Very high

Normal

Lower than average

Low

II. Motivation

1. How would you rate your motivation to continue working in this workplace?

Very motivated

Somewhat motivated

Somewhat unmotivated

Unmotivated

2. How important is financial incentive (salary) at work to you among other factors?

Most important

Quite important

Not very important

Not important at all

3. How strongly do you feel an inner desire to make the world a better place through your work?

Very strongly

In some way strongly

Don't feel it very much

Don't feel it at all

4. Is it important for you to increase your social status through work?

Very important

Quite important

Not very important

Not important at all

5. How important are professional development and professional development to you in your work?

- Extremely important
- Quite important
- Not very important
- Not important at all

6. To what extent are you motivated to work by the opportunity to work on interesting and meaningful projects?

- Very motivated
- In some way motivated
- Not very motivated
- Not motivated at all

7. How important is the social mission of your organization to you?

- Very important
- Quite important
- Not very important
- Not important at all

8. To what extent does the psychological climate in your company and relationships with colleagues / stakeholders help you work now?

- They help a lot
- They help in some way
- Not very helpful
- They do not help at all

9. To what extent does your motivation to work depend on the recognition of your achievements in the company?

- It depends on a lot
- It somewhat depends
- It doesn't really depend
- Does not depend at all

10. How important is the significance of your work for society to you?

- Very important
- Relatively important
- Not very important

Not important at all

11. Would you now accept a new position in the commercial sector?

Yes

No

12. If so, which of the following would make you change your job to a new position in the commercial sector now? Choose one option.

Better pay

Possibility of professional development

Higher significance of work

More interesting tasks

Better interpersonal relationships in a team

Better stakeholder relations

Greater recognition by managers

Higher social status

I don't want to change jobs

Other (please specify _____)

13. Which of the following motivates you to stay in this workplace and not change it to work in the commercial sector? Choose one option.

Good pay

Possibility of professional development

High significance of work

Interesting work tasks

Good relations with colleagues

Good relations with stakeholders

Recognition by managers

The high social status I get thanks to this job

Other (please specify _____)

14. What motivates you to continue working in this place, even in case of high stress or heavy workload? Choose the most important factors for you.

Financial bonuses

The possibility of professional development

Awareness of the importance of work

Interesting tasks

Good relations with colleagues

Recognition by managers

- Awareness of one's social status due to belonging to this company
- Nothing motivates
- Other (please specify _____)

III. Questions Regarding Mortality

1. How important is it to you that your work leaves a legacy for the future?
 - Very important
 - Somewhat important
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all

2. To which extent is your work associated with the desire to contribute to the future generations?
 - Very much
 - Somewhat much
 - Not much
 - Not associated

3. How often do you contemplate your own mortality (as a person's ability to die)?
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Seldom
 - Never

4. How often do you contemplate the mortality of others (like family, friends, all humanity)?
 - Often
 - Sometimes
 - Seldom
 - Never

5. To what extent is it important for you to be as one human group with people you help / the memorialization of which you are engaged in professionally?
 - Very important
 - Somewhat important
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all

6. How important is it to you to care for others (not only in your professional life, but in everyday life as well)?
- Very important
 - Somewhat important
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all
7. How important is the connection with people from the past, as if you are part of humanity?
- Very important
 - Somewhat important
 - Not very important
 - Not important at all
8. Do you want to be remembered after your death?
- Yes, I really want to be remembered by many people from my life
 - Yes, I want to be remembered, but I'm fine if only by my relatives and closes friends
 - It doesn't really bother me, but it would be nice if someone could recall me after my death
 - No, I don't see the importance to be remembered after death
9. Whom do you want to be remembered by?
- Everyone – colleagues, friends, family, I even wish I could have a street named after me or a museum, etc.
 - I want my friends, close colleagues, and relatives remember me
 - I have only few people I want to be remembered by, other don't care me
 - I don't want people to remember me
10. Has the frequency of your contemplative about life and death changed in the context of your work?
- Have started to think much more than before the work
 - Have started to think a bit more than before the work
 - It hasn't changed, I have the same frequency as before
 - It hasn't changed, I didn't think about the work before
11. How much has the understanding of mortality / limited time in your life affected you, your motivation, your relationship with others, etc.?
- Very much
 - Somewhat much

- Not much
- Doesn't influence

12. Has your work influenced your perception of other people in comparison to your perception before starting the work?

- Yes, my work has increased my empathy and awareness of human suffering and memorialization
- My work has somewhat increased my empathy and understanding of human suffering and memorialization
- My work has provided some insights, but it hasn't profoundly changed my perception
- No, my work hasn't significantly influenced my perception of others
- Other (please specify _____)

13. How much your perception of your own mortality and limitation of human life influences your desire to work in the field of memorialization/?

- Very much
- Somewhat much
- Not much
- Doesn't influence / Don't think about it

14. If your contemplative about life and death changed in the context of your work, could you specify how? (open question, optional)

15. If you are interested in continuing this research and agree to participate in an interview, please leave your contact details.